

Finding the Optimum

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Abstract

A robust non-parametric method is described for locating the optimum in a given list of values. The method entails first ranking the values. A linear function is then fitted to the values that maps rank to position in the list. The function is used to calculate the expected position of the value with maximum rank.

Introduction

Suppose that we have an algorithm that processes data in real time. We have available a large dataset of representative historical data on which we measure the performance of the algorithm using some suitable scale. The algorithm has a single tunable parameter which we would like to adjust dynamically as the database grows in order to achieve the likely best result on as yet unseen data. However, it is computationally infeasible to measure the performance repeatedly from scratch over the entire dataset in real time. Therefore we instead maintain a limited number of copies of the algorithm, each with a different parameter setting. We update them in parallel in real time as each new item of data is received. Our task is to determine from their respective performance scores the best current setting to use.

In general we are given a non-empty list L of n resulting performance values, $[v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{n-1}]$, that appear to span the optimum as the parameter is increased. Optimization is straightforward if performance is a deterministic smooth function of the tunable parameter and there are no local maxima, but this is often not the case and we do not assume that here. For example, suppose that the results we obtain are the following where $n=12$.

$$L = [-29.45, -1.29, 0.02, -0.31, 0.19, 0.78, 0.56, 0.45, 0.67, 0.33, -1.29, -3.60]$$

The values are plotted in Figure 1. Notice that the first value is an extreme outlier and is off the scale of the graph. In order to minimize the influence of such outliers and also to weaken any assumptions about the particular underlying functional dependence of the performance measure on the parameter setting, let us replace each value v_k by its rank r_k where $0 \leq r_k \leq n-1$. See Figure 2 for a plot of the ranks. If, as in our example, two or more values are identical, then we average their ranks. So, we obtain

Index (k)	Value (v_k)	Rank (r_k)
0	-29.45	0
1	-1.29	2.5
2	0.02	5
3	-0.31	4
4	0.19	6
5	0.78	11
6	0.56	9
7	0.45	8
8	0.67	10
9	0.33	7
10	-1.29	2.5
11	-3.60	1

Notice that the ranks (save for averaged ties) are a permutation of the indices. The optimization task reduces to estimating the index for which the expected rank after arbitrary fluctuations have been removed is the maximum: $n-1$ or 11 in our example. Now, if the results have roughly spanned the optimum, the lowest ranks will be those of both the smallest and highest indices. The highest ranks will be those of mid-range index. This suggests that we regress the index k on the rank r_k and fit a linear function $f(r) = \alpha r + \beta$ that maps the rank to the average corresponding index. We then use the function to calculate the index $f(n-1)$ for which the rank is $n-1$. Since in general this index is not a whole number, we estimate the best value by interpolation between the two adjacent values in the original list. Calculation of $f(n-1)$ is quite straightforward and we can take advantage of several useful properties. We simply state them in the next section and consign their proofs to the appendix on page 9.

Figure 1: *Plot of value (v_k) against index (k) of worked example L .*

Figure 2: Plot of rank (r_k) against index (k) of worked example L .

Some Properties

Even in the presence of ties, the linear function $f(r)$ always passes through the centroid $(\frac{n-1}{2}, \frac{n-1}{2})$. Therefore, the function actually has only one degree of freedom and is completely defined by its gradient α :

$$f(r) = \alpha \left(r - \frac{n-1}{2} \right) + \frac{n-1}{2} \quad (1)$$

Provided that not all n values in L are identical (in which case both the numerator and the denominator below are zero), the least-squares gradient is given by

$$\alpha = \frac{N}{D} \quad (2)$$

where

$$N = \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k \right) - \frac{n(n-1)^2}{4} \quad (3)$$

$$D = \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2 \right) - \frac{n(n-1)^2}{4} \quad (4)$$

The optimum index $f(n-1)$ is given by

$$f(n-1) = \frac{(\alpha + 1)(n-1)}{2} \quad (5)$$

and it follows that the optimum index, although not necessarily an integer, lies in the range $0 \leq f(n-1) \leq (n-1)$ even if some ranks are tied.

Example

Let us now find the optimum for our example, L . We simply calculate the squares of the ranks and the products of the ranks and indices.

Index (k)	Rank (r_k)	Product ($r_k k$)	Square (r_k^2)
0	0	0	0
1	2.5	2.5	6.25
2	5	10	25
3	4	12	16
4	6	24	36
5	11	55	121
6	9	54	81
7	8	56	64
8	10	80	100
9	7	63	49
10	2.5	25	6.25
11	1	11	1
Total:		392.5	505.5

Now, since $n = 12$,

$$\frac{n(n-1)^2}{4} = 363$$

Therefore, to four decimal places,

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \frac{392.5 - 363}{505.5 - 363} \\ &= 0.2070 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} f(n-1) &= \frac{(0.2070 + 1)(12 - 1)}{2} \\ &= 6.6386 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3 plots the projection of the optimum index for example L . Notice that the graph is rotated through 90° because the index is regressed on the rank rather than the other way around. The linear function f passes through the centroid and projects onto an expected index of 6.6386 at maximum rank.

Figure 3: *Projection of optimum index of worked example L.*

Validity

The optimum index is a valid estimate only if the range of values L has captured the peak. If so, the residuals with low rank have large magnitude and those with high rank have small. The reverse applies if L spans a trough rather than a peak. Therefore a useful statistical measure of validity is the following.

$$\mathcal{V} = 24n^{-5/2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} |f(r_k) - k| \left(\frac{n-1}{2} - r_k \right) \quad (6)$$

For large n the statistic has an approximately standard normal distribution. Figure 4 shows a P-P plot that compares the cumulative distribution of \mathcal{V} to that of the standard normal. The distribution of \mathcal{V} with $n=10000$ was sampled 100000 times by Monte Carlo simulation. For comparison, the identity function is shown in the background as a red line. Notice that there is almost exact superimposition.

Table 1 provides critical values of the statistic for various n . The columns are the probabilities of \mathcal{V} being as high as the corresponding critical value by chance if the rank vector were drawn randomly from the uniform distribution in which every vector is equally likely. The critical values do not necessarily increase monotonically in each column because for small n the number of distinct possible values of \mathcal{V} is small. For $n > 200$ the values are those of the standard normal distribution. Table 2 shows the calculation for our example L , noting that $n=12$ and $\alpha=0.2070$. Notice that $\mathcal{V}=2.8874$ and so, with reference to Table 1, is highly significant ($p \leq 0.01$).

Figure 4: *P-P plot of validity statistic against standard normal distribution. The identity reference is shown in red.*

Table 1: *Critical values of \mathcal{V} statistic.*

n	$p \leq 0.1$	$p \leq 0.05$	$p \leq 0.02$	$p \leq 0.01$
4	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.28
5	1.12	1.72	1.80	1.81
6	1.32	1.64	1.98	2.12
7	1.26	1.67	2.01	2.21
8	1.26	1.62	2.00	2.20
9	1.29	1.63	2.01	2.23
10	1.28	1.63	2.01	2.20
11	1.28	1.63	2.00	2.23
12	1.28	1.64	2.00	2.22
15	1.28	1.63	2.02	2.25
20	1.29	1.65	2.02	2.28
50	1.30	1.65	2.04	2.31
100	1.29	1.66	2.07	2.33
200	1.29	1.65	2.08	2.33
>200	1.28	1.64	2.05	2.33

Index (k)	Rank (r_k)	Function ($f(r_k)$)	Term ($ f(r_k) - k \left(\frac{n-1}{2} - r_k\right)$)
0	0	4.3614	23.9877
1	2.5	4.8789	11.6368
2	5	5.3965	1.6982
3	4	5.1895	3.2842
4	6	5.6035	-0.8018
5	11	6.6386	-9.0123
6	9	6.2246	-0.7860
7	8	6.0175	-2.4561
8	10	6.4316	-7.0579
9	7	5.8105	-4.7842
10	2.5	4.8789	15.3632
11	1	4.5684	28.9421
Total =			60.0140
$\times 24n^{-5/2} =$			2.8874

Table 2: *Calculation of validity of example L.*

Interpolation

The final step having calculated and validated $f(n-1)$, assuming that it is of interest, is to estimate the associated performance score from the original list L . Since in general the estimated index is not a whole number this required interpolation. So, for our example we have

$$\begin{aligned} f(n-1) &= 6.6386 \\ L[6] &= 0.56 \\ L[7] &= 0.45 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore we conclude that with setting 6.6386, the score would be

$$6.6386 \times 0.56 + (1 - 6.6386) \times 0.45 = 0.5202$$

Figure 5 shows this graphically.

Summary

In summary therefore, given a list of scores L , we calculate the best setting as follows.

1. Determine α (Equation 2) using Equations 3 and 4.
2. Calculate the validity statistic \mathcal{V} using Equation 6.

Figure 5: Plot of value (v_k) against index (k) of worked example L .

3. Check that \mathcal{V} indicates that the result is valid according to the required level of confidence by reference to Table 1.
4. If so, calculate the best setting using Equation 5.
5. If it is of interest, estimate the associated score by reference to the original list of scores L and interpolation as shown above.

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Appendix

Lemma 1 (Centroid)

Even if ranks are tied, the least-squares function f passes through the centroid.

$$\vdash f\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right) = \frac{n-1}{2}$$

Proof

The total square error E is given by

$$E = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (\alpha r_k + \beta - k)^2$$

The normal form equation expressed in matrix notation that minimizes E is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} 1 & \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k \\ \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k & \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \beta \\ \alpha \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} k \\ \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k \end{bmatrix}$$

Equivalently, noting that the sum of the ranks is the same as that of the indices, even in the presence of ties,

$$\begin{bmatrix} n & \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \\ \frac{n(n-1)}{2} & \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \beta \\ \alpha \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \\ \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \beta \\ \alpha \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{\det} \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2 & -\frac{n(n-1)}{2} \\ -\frac{n(n-1)}{2} & n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \\ \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k \end{bmatrix}$$

where the determinant is given by

$$\det = n \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2 \right) - \frac{n^2(n-1)^2}{4}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} f\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right) &= \alpha \frac{n-1}{2} + \beta \\ &= \frac{\left(n \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k \right) - \frac{n^2(n-1)^2}{4} \right) \frac{n-1}{2} + \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2 \right) - \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k \right)}{n \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2 \right) - \frac{n^2(n-1)^2}{4}} \\ &= \frac{n-1}{2} \left(\frac{4 \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k \right) - n(n-1)^2 + 4 \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2 \right) - 4 \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k \right)}{4 \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2 \right) - n(n-1)^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{n-1}{2} \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 2 (Gradient)

Even if ranks are tied, the least-squares gradient is given by

$$\vdash \alpha = \frac{\left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k\right) - \frac{n(n-1)^2}{4}}{\left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2\right) - \frac{n(n-1)^2}{4}}$$

Proof

From the proof of Lemma 1

$$\alpha = \frac{n \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k\right) - \frac{n^2(n-1)^2}{4}}{n \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2\right) - \frac{n^2(n-1)^2}{4}}$$

The result then follows immediately from division of both numerator and denominator by n . \square

Lemma 3 (Inequality)

Even if ranks are tied,

$$\vdash \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k \leq \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2$$

Proof

In the absence of ties, the rank vector is simply a permutation of the sequence of indices. Therefore, in that case, the result follows immediately from the Cauchy-Schwarz Inequality. However, if ranks are tied and replaced by their average, the LHS of the inequality above is a maximum when the rank increases monotonically with index. In other words when

$$\forall j, k : 0 \dots n-1 \bullet j < k \implies r_j \leq r_k$$

This is easily shown. Suppose that the rank is non-monotonic. That means that for some j and k where $j < k$, we have that $r_j > r_k$. If we swap the two indices then the sum on the LHS increases by

$$\begin{aligned} (r_j k + r_k j) - (r_j j + r_k k) &= (r_j - r_k)(k - j) \\ &> 0 \end{aligned}$$

Since permutation of indices has no effect on the sum on the RHS of the inequality, we need show only that the inequality holds for monotonic ranking, the permutation for which the LHS is maximum. Now, if the ranking is monotonic, replacement of a set of contiguous ranks by their average preserves the inequality as is easily shown. In the absence of ties, the rank is equal to the index and the inequality holds as a direct consequence of the Cauchy-Schwarz Inequality. Suppose now that we average the ranks of the h elements with indices (and hence ranks) j to $j+h-1$, inclusive. This increases the non-negative difference between the RHS and the LHS

by

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\sum_{k=j}^{j+h-1} \left(j + \frac{h-1}{2} \right) k \right) - \left(\sum_{k=j}^{j+h-1} \left(j + \frac{h-1}{2} \right)^2 \right) \\
&= \left(j + \frac{h-1}{2} \right) \left(\sum_{k=j}^{j+h-1} k \right) - \left(j + \frac{h-1}{2} \right)^2 h \\
&= \left(j + \frac{h-1}{2} \right) \left(\frac{(j+h-1)(j+h)}{2} - \frac{(j-1)j}{2} - \left(j + \frac{h-1}{2} \right) h \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (2j+h-1) \left((j+h-1)(j+h) - (j-1)j - (2j+h-1)h \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (2j+h-1) (j^2 + 2jh + h^2 - j - h - j^2 + j - 2jh + h^2 - h) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} (2j+h-1) h (h-1) \\
&\geq 0
\end{aligned}$$

The inequality is thus preserved. \square

Lemma 4 (Positivity)

Provided that not all n values in L are identical, the denominator of the gradient (Equation 4) is positive.

$$\vdash \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2 > \frac{n(n-1)^2}{4}$$

Proof

If all the values in L are identical then all n have the same rank, $\frac{n-1}{2}$. In this case the denominator of α is zero. Any or all of the ties are eliminated by repeatedly partitioning the tied ranks into distinct ties. At each iteration the denominator strictly increases. Thus suppose that for some rank r and positive integers a and b , ranks r to $r+a+b-1$ inclusive are tied and replaced by their average, $r + \frac{a+b-1}{2}$. We partition these into two separately tied ranges, r to $r+a-1$ and $r+a$ to $r+a+b-1$. The denominator D increases by

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\sum_{r'=r}^{r+a-1} \left(r + \frac{a-1}{2} \right)^2 \right) + \left(\sum_{r'=r+a}^{r+a+b-1} \left(r + a + \frac{b-1}{2} \right)^2 \right) - \left(\sum_{r'=r}^{r+a+b-1} \left(r + \frac{a+b-1}{2} \right)^2 \right) \\
&= a \left(r + \frac{a-1}{2} \right)^2 + b \left(r + a + \frac{b-1}{2} \right)^2 - (a+b) \left(r + \frac{a+b-1}{2} \right)^2 \\
&= ar^2 + ar(a-1) + \frac{a(a-1)^2}{4} + br^2 + ba^2 + \frac{b(b-1)^2}{4} + 2bra + br(b-1) + ba(b-1) \\
&\quad - (a+b)r^2 - (a+b)r(a+b-1) - \frac{(a+b)(a+b-1)^2}{4} \\
&= r^2(a+b-(a+b)) + r(a^2-a+2ba+b^2-b-a^2-ab+a-ba-b^2+b) \\
&\quad + \frac{a^3-2a^2+a+4ba^2+b^3-2b^2+b+4b^2a-4ba-(a+b)(a^2+b^2+1+2ab-2a-2b)}{4} \\
&= \frac{a^3-2a^2+a+4b^2a+b^3-2b^2+b+4ba^2-4ba-a^3-ab^2-a-2a^2b+2a^2+2ab-ba^2-b^3-b-2b^2a+2ba+2b^2}{4} \\
&= \frac{b^2a+a^2b}{4} \\
&= \frac{ab(a+b)}{4} \\
&> 0
\end{aligned}$$

\square

Lemma 5 (Bounds)

Provided that not all n values in L are identical, the magnitude of the least-squares gradient α is no greater than unity.

$$\vdash |\alpha| \leq 1$$

Proof

Now, restating Equation 2, where N and D are defined by Equations 3 and 4, respectively,

$$\alpha = \frac{N}{D}$$

We show that the sum of the numerator and denominator is non-negative. We achieve this by making the substitution $k' = n-1-k$ which corresponds to reversing the indices but without changing the ranks.

$$\begin{aligned} N + D &= \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2\right) + \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k\right) - \frac{n(n-1)^2}{2} \\ &= \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2\right) + \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k (n-1-k')\right) - \frac{n(n-1)^2}{2} \\ &= \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2\right) - \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k'\right) + \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k (n-1)\right) - \frac{n(n-1)^2}{2} \\ &= \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2\right) - \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k'\right) + (n-1) \left(\left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k\right) - \frac{n(n-1)}{2}\right) \\ &= \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k^2\right) - \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} r_k k'\right) \\ &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, from the above result and Lemma 3,

$$-D \leq N \leq D$$

Noting that D is positive (Lemma 4), it follows that

$$-1 \leq \frac{N}{D} \leq 1$$

□

Lemma 6 (Range)

Provided that not all n values in L are identical, the optimum index is non-negative and bounded above by $n-1$.

$$\vdash 0 \leq f(n-1) \leq n-1$$

Proof

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq \frac{(\alpha+1)(n-1)}{2} && \dots \alpha+1 \geq 0 \text{ (Lemma 5)} \\ &= f(n-1) && \dots \text{Equation 5} \\ &= \frac{(\alpha+1)(n-1)}{2} && \dots \text{Equation 5} \\ &\leq n-1 && \dots \alpha+1 \leq 2 \text{ (Lemma 5)} \end{aligned}$$

□

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